

Intravenous Fluid Administration During Colorectal Surgery

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Background

- 320,000 colorectal surgery cases in the US annually
- Implementing fluid management strategies may decrease rates of postoperative complications
- 2018 Enhanced Recovery After Surgery (ERAS) Society guideline updates: Goal Directed Fluid Therapy (GDFT) and Zero-Balance Fluid Therapy (ZBFT) improve patient outcomes
- Evidence shows decrease compliance with evidence-based guidelines for intravenous (IV) fluid administration in this population

Purpose and Aims

- Develop a protocol proposal based on recent ERAS guidelines to guide anesthesia providers with IV fluid administration during colorectal surgery
- Create an educational module for anesthesia providers on the proposed protocol, which includes a pretest and posttest to evaluate its effectiveness
- Performance target goal: To increase >50% of participants' posttest scores by 50% from pretest or for >50% of them to achieve a score of ≥70% in the posttest

Methods

- **Design:** single cohort, prospective, quality improvement project
- **Setting:** Kaiser Permanente Fontana and Ontario
- **Sample:** Anesthesiologists and CRNAs
- **Module:** Created with Articulate 360 software and published on Moodle platform
- **Implementation:** Online learning module with ERAS-based fluid therapy protocol
- **Evaluation:** Pretest and posttest scores

Conceptual Framework: The Iowa Model

- Set of clinical decision points that guide healthcare project development and quality improvement
- Steps include identifying issues/opportunities for research, stating question or purpose, forming a project team, assembling and synthesizing a body of research evidence, designing and piloting practice change, interpreting and sustaining change, and disseminating results

IV Fluid Therapy Algorithm for Colorectal Surgery

Considerations:
*Protocol should not affect blood product administration:
If actively bleeding:
-Transfuse pRBCs to maintain Hgb >7g/dL
-Administer additional FFP and platelets PRN
Other options to treat hypotension when PVI/SVV is low:
-Vasopressors, decreasing depth of anesthesia.

Literature Review

- 2018 ERAS Guidelines
- Goal Directed Fluid Therapy and Zero-Balance Fluid Therapy
- IV Fluid Therapy Selection
- Protocol Development

Discussion

- Achieved project's goal to increase >50% of participant posttest scores by 50% from pretest scores
- Goal reached: 89% of participants achieved a score of ≥70% in the posttest.
- Online learning module software can be an effective tool for educating anesthesia providers on clinical practice updates

Limitations

- Authors' lack of experience using online learning module software
- Module was only open to participants for one month due to time constraints

Implications & Recommendations

Implications:

- This project may be used to develop a systemwide protocol for fluid administration in colorectal surgery and measuring compliance with the protocol

Recommendations:

- Track quality improvement indicators and outcomes related to use of a GDFT protocol in this population
- Compare effectiveness of various online learning module software options
- Additional incentives to improve anesthesia provider compliance with ERAS recommendations

Results

Score of Pre-Module Test, Post-Module, and the Increase from Pre Module to Post-module:
The mean increase from Pre- to Post- was 4.4 with $p < 0.0001$.

Test	Mean Score ±SD	P Value
Pre_Module	3.8±2.0	
Post_Module	8.2±1.2	
Post_Module - Pre_Module	4.4±2.0	<0.0001

*p value was generated by Wilcoxon signed rank test

